

USE OF PHRASEOLOGISMS IN POEMS

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Abstract. This article discusses the artist's ability to provide expressiveness through phraseology in poetic works. Scientific opinions on the subject are proved and analyzed on the example of Farida Afro'z's poetic works.

Keywords: phraseologism, semantic development, phraseological meaning, emotional color, poetic work.

A language unit consisting of two or more words and expressing a single meaning is called a phraseological unit or phraseologism. Although phraseologisms are in the form of a word combination or a sentence, as they consist of more than one word, they are completely different from these units, which are speech units, and as a lexical unit, they are close to words in many ways.

Phraseologisms are not formed in the process of speech, like phrases or sentences, but they, like words, are ready-made in the language. Here, more than one word as a whole undergoes semantic development based on a certain image, by means of transfer. Such a superimposed figurative meaning, created on the basis of a certain image, is called a phraseological meaning... a phraseological unit is formed on the basis of a specific opposition and unity of the plan of expression and the plan of content. Idioms are often synonymous with lexemes, and with an excess of semantic and emotional color, they are at the top of the synonymous line.

As you can see, phraseologisms are created with expressive paint from the moment they appear in the language. So, first of all, expressions are used in order to achieve effectiveness in speech:

a) Bormasam bo'lmaydi, **ko'zlar to'rt bo'ldi**,
Yo'limga termular marmartosh ichra . (Farida Afro'z)

b) Otang
bo'lsa duogo'y, onang-chi, balogardon,
Etaklarin
ko'zingga surtmoqlik ham baxt erur.

O'rab
qolsa mushkulot, **tushib qolsang domiga**,
Shu

tugunni shu bugun **yechmoqlik** ham baxt erur. (Farida Afro'z)

The role and importance of phraseological expressions is incomparable in the pictorial representation of reality and its clear and full embodiment before the eyes of the reader. Phrases are unique figurative expressions of conclusions drawn by the people based on observation of events in life, evaluation of acceptable and unacceptable actions in society, summarization of life experiences. Phrases are more common in oral speech. Therefore, in poetic speech, it is used to approach oral speech and to simplify speech:

a) Derazamni yopaman, **etim uchadi**,
Jondan o'tar,

izg'irin,

shamol... (Farida Afro'z)

b) Yetar bas, *diydamni tosh qilaman*, endi,

Qaytarib olaman ko'nglimni sendan,

Sevib, yonib, kuyib, charchamadi bu yurak,

Osmonga otaman uni, quyosh qilaman, endi. (Farida Afro'z)

d) Dunyoda hech narsa bejiz bo'lmagay,

Bejizga sendan ham *qolmagan ko'nglim*. (Farida Afro'z)

Phraseologisms, as mentioned above, are convenient to use because they have appeared in the language itself for a long time. They can create a high level of economy and expressiveness by figuratively condensing words that can be used instead of phrases. It also creates a great opportunity for the thought to fully reach the speaker's goal:

a) Dushmanim ayyordir, *paytlar poylaydi*,

Do'stim esa nodon, *suvni loylaydi*,

Ikkisi bir bo'lib *ko'zim boylaydi*,

Men ularni kechiray, bir qudrat bergin,

Allohim, mehringdan bir xilvat bergin. (Farida Afro'z)

d) Qanday yaxshi seni sog'insa kimdir,

Yuragi ezilib kutsa, intilsa,

Hoh u singling bo'lsin, hohi iningdir,

Yana ham yaxshi-ku *yetti yot* bo'lsa. (Farida Afro'z)

e) Nechun shuncha sarsonlik,

Taqdirga tan bermasdan!

Yana *qildi tavakkal*,

Ortga qaytish yo'q, also. (Farida Afro'z)

Writers are usually not content with choosing and using phrases to suit the purpose of the image. Perhaps, characters change and rework according to their nature, mental state, lifestyle. In this way, folk expressions are polished and saturated with new subtleties of meaning. There are many different ways of processing folk expressions, giving them a new color and tone, a new interpretation of meaning. This includes methods such as "opening up a new interpretation of the meaning of a general phrase, changing the lexical structure of the phrase and expanding its semantic-stylistic functions, adding new figurative and figurative meanings to the phrase." Various methods of processing phraseological expressions have been widely studied by B. Yoldoshev. The most common ones in the literary text are as follows: 1. Replacement of some words in the phrase; 2. Expanding the content of the phrase; 3. Shortening the content of the phrase. Omitting some words in the phrase is done with the requirement of economy in the language. But writers use it for their artistic purposes.

In the study of expressions used in a work of art, it is necessary to determine the quantity (foundation) of phrases within a work and classify them according to their characteristic features, to describe them structurally and semantically, and to check their function in the text. In such an analysis, the writer's ability to use available language units is also revealed.

Words, language units in general are used in unusual constructions, for example, the meanings are contradictory, or vice versa, expressions with similar meanings are used in opposite ways, extraordinary unique images and images are created.

These tools appear before our eyes, first of all, as an opportunity to demonstrate the broad semantic and stylistic variety of our native language through fiction. We observe this when most words are used figuratively in the literary text and their semantic meaning expands. That is, the language of an artistic work, in particular, a poetic work, becomes a field that can reveal even the most subtle aspects of the national language with the help of these tools.

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